

ON THE BENDING BEHAVIORS OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS FILLED WITH AN ELASTIC CORE

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to investigate the behaviours of fiber-reinforced composite cylindrical structures subjected to pure bending moment. Under a large transverse deflection, ovalization of the circular cross-section may occur. In addition, local instability so called local buckling can also be induced on the compression side of ovalized tubular structures. Excessive cross-sectional distortion and local instability lead to catastrophic failure but they can be prolonged by inserting a low density elastic material into the hollow cylinder. In order to investigate the cross-sectional and flexural deformations of the composite cylindrical structure filled with an elastic core the minimum potential energy principle in association with the Ritz method is used. The strain energy comprises the stored energy in the cylindrical shell and that of the solid core. The cylinder and core are kinematically constrained to deform altogether by using the continuous displacement functions between the shell-core interfaces. External work is given by applied moments at the both ends, of which cross-section can deform freely. Geometric nonlinearities are included in the model to be able to capture ovalization. Local buckling is predicted by solving the stability equations of a cylindrical composite shell element supported with an elastic foundation contributed from the core material. Stiffness of the foundation is estimated by employing three dimensional theory of elasticity via the method of Maxwell stress functions that allows wavelengths of the buckled form in both axial and circumferential directions. Various fiber orientations are studied such as the angle ply and quasi-isotropic laminates. The computational results show that the shells with an insertion of core exhibit much higher critical moments due to ovalization and local instability than the ones with the absence of core. A harmonious interaction between shell and core can potentially reduce weight and maintain high structural integrity, functionality, and efficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cylindrical shells are widely used in engineering structures to carry and withstand a variety of external loads. Among several types of loading condition, bending is the most common one encountered in all thin-wall lightweight structures. Normally, major curvature is induced due to the application of flexure as schematically illustrated in Fig. 1(a) when curvature κ' is developed in the x -direction of a cylindrical structure subjected to moment M along the same direction. However, apart from the overall flexural deformation, the circular cross-section of the cylinder can be susceptible to ovalization shown in Fig. 1(b). This phenomenon is also known as Brazier effect because it was L.G. Brazier [1] who initially studied the ovalizing mechanism for the case of isotropic and homogeneous cylinders. Brazier created a two dimensional mathematical model of shells as ring-type structures based on the variational method and revealed that there was nonlinear response in moment-curvature relation resulting from ovalization and hence, loss of bending stiffness. Also predicted was the critical point or the limit point instability, where the maximum moment occurred. Calladine [2] later reformulated the Brazier's equation in terms of ovalization degree (ζ) and curvature (κ'). The potential energy proposed by Calladine was expressed in eq. (1), where area moment of inertia (I) explicitly appeared in the first term contributing to the flexural strain energy. Due to distorted cross-section, the

area moment of inertia was written in term of ovalization degree in eq. (2). Calladine, nonetheless, neglected the second order term of ovalization (the underlined term) in eq. (2) and obtained the same bending response as previously found by Brazier. Thus, Brazier and Calladine models are first order ovalization model (FOM), whereas those with the inclusion of second order term can be called as second order ovalization model (SOM).

$$U = \frac{1}{2}EI(\kappa')^2 + \frac{3\pi EH^3\zeta^2}{8(1-\nu^2)R_m} \quad (1)$$

$$I = \int_A (R_m \cos \theta + \eta)^2 dA = \int_0^{2\pi} (R_m \cos \theta + \eta)^2 R_m H d\theta = \pi R_m^3 H \left(1 - \frac{3}{2}\zeta + \frac{5}{8}\zeta^2\right) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Bending of cylindrical shell with deformable cross-section.

Tatting [3], [4] extended the preceding investigations of the flexural behaviours of cylinders to examine composite cylindrical shells with the assumptions of semi-membrane and inextensional circumference. In the case of long isotropic tubes, Tatting's results agreed well with the Brazier's findings. Tatting also studied local instability of cylindrical shells and found that the local buckling usually occurs before the ovalization limit point. Effect of material orthotropy on bending behaviours was investigated by Wadee, et.al. [5]. Shear modulus and Poisson's ratio were varied to observe their effect on local instability of the ovalized tube subjected to bending moment. Karamanos [6], [7] was investigated transversely-isotropic both of them found that the local buckling always occur before the limit point is reached. Moreover, bending behaviour of cylindrical shell is published widely by several researchers [8]-[11].

They have many solution to increasing bending resistance. Increasing the area moment of inertia is ones solution such as increase wall thickness or increasing the radius. The others solution, Filled with another elastic material in a hollow shell can be improved the bending resistance too. G.N.Karam [12] was studied the bending behaviour of isotropic cylindrical ring filled with an elastic core based on Brazier's approach for ovalization phenomena with a simplified energy equations in two-dimensional. For a local buckling phenomena, normal stress in compressive side was compared to critical compressive stress of axisymmetric buckling. His result shown that the moment to cause local buckling is always lower than the ovalization limit point or Brazier moment. A.G. Arani [13] was investigated elastic stability of isotropic cylindrical shell filled with an elastic core under axial compression based on energy method. Elastic spring coefficient of foundation model was chosen to resemble as the elastic core. Consequently, cylindrical shell with an elastic core have higher buckling load than hollow cylinder and its increased elastic stability of the structure.

The goal of this paper is to determine the complete effect of material and geometric parameters on the bending response and local buckling loads of finite length composite cylinders inserted with an elastic solid material. In section 2, the principle of minimum total potential energy and the Ritz's approach is chosen to investigate the flexural behaviours of composite shells with symmetric balanced laminate. The stored energy of structures is separated in two main parts. Cylindrical shell strain energy is formulated in term of curved surface element with Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis for thin shell. Inextensional cross-section and semi-membrane assumptions previously adopted in the literatures are relaxed so the model can freely capture the influences of whole in-plane material anisotropy on the structural response. Energy storage in an elastic core is formulated by treating the material as a three-dimensional solid element, with kinematically compatible deformation fields at the shell-core interface. In section 3, local buckling in composite cylindrical structures filled with an elastic core is investigated by utilizing Trefftz criterion. Equivalent cylinder approach is considered to account for local radius change of the cross-section. Contributed from the core material, elastic foundation of cylindrical shells is modelled from three-dimensional Maxwell stress function, which can allow buckling wave form to occur in both longitudinal and circumferential directions. In section 4, the numerical results of the models are shown and compared to finite-element method in some cases. Effects of variation in length to cylinder radius ratio, thickness to cylinder radius ratio, and core modulus to longitudinal effective shell modulus ratio are studied.

2 GLOBAL BENDING RESPONSE AND OVALIZATION

In this study, the composite cylindrical shell considered has a uniform thickness (H), mean radius (R_m), and length (L). The shell consists of 8-ply balanced symmetric laminate. The lamination parameters are represented in term of ABD-matrix. Hollow space of the cylinder is completely filled with an isotropic elastic material, whose properties are defined by Young's modulus (E_c) and Poisson ratio (ν_c). An energy equation is formulated to study the bending response of the structure. The minimum potential energy principle in association with the Ritz's method is used to predict the structural response. The total potential energy of the composite cylindrical shell filled with an elastic core is the sum of three parts as expressed in eq. (3).

$$V = U_{shell} + U_{core} - W \quad (3)$$

The first term is energy storage or strain energy in composite cylindrical shell (U_{shell}). The second is strain energy in elastic core (U_{core}) and the last term is contributed from work done (W) due to the bending moment applied at the both ends. Amongst the terms shown in the potential energy equation, work-done is the most straightforward and can be computed from the product of external moment (M) and both ends rotation (Ω) as shown in eq. (4), whereas the more involved formulations of the strain energies are presented in the next two subsections.

$$W = 2M\Omega = 2M \left(-\frac{\partial v^\circ}{\partial x} \right) \Big|_{x=L/2, \theta=\frac{\pi}{2}} \quad (4)$$

In the above equation v° is denoted for circumferential displacement. Superscript ($^\circ$) indicates that the displacement is evaluated in the reference plane. Note that in this section all kinematic variables are referenced with the inner surface of the shell because the deformation fields in the longitudinal, circumferential, and radial directions ($u^\circ, v^\circ, w^\circ$) must be continuous at the shell-core interface. Consequently, the force resultants (N_{ij}), moment resultants (M_{ij}), and ABD-matrix in the following equations are calculated based on the interfacial surface as the reference plane.

2.1 Energy storage in composite cylindrical shell

The strain energy stored in a cylindrical shell can be written in eq. (5). Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis is adopted because the thin shell assumption is considered. The shell has the thickness to radius ratio less than 0.1 ($H/R_m \leq 0.1$).

$$U_{shell} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \int_0^{2\pi} (N_x \varepsilon_x^\circ + N_\theta \varepsilon_\theta^\circ + N_{x\theta} \gamma_{x\theta}^\circ + M_x \kappa_x^\circ + M_\theta \kappa_\theta^\circ + M_{x\theta} \kappa_{x\theta}^\circ) R_i d\theta dx \quad (5)$$

In the above, N_x , N_θ and $N_{x\theta}$ are in-plane components of force resultants N_{ij} . M_x , M_θ and $M_{x\theta}$ are bending components and twisting component of moment resultants M_{ij} , respectively. The constitutive model presented in eq. (6) relates the force-moment resultants to the strains-curvatures on the reference plane.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \{N_{ij}\} \\ \{M_{ij}\} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A_{ij}] & [B_{ij}] \\ [B_{ij}] & [D_{ij}] \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\varepsilon_{ij}^\circ\} \\ \{\kappa_{ij}^\circ\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In eq. (6), A-matrix is stretching stiffness matrix, B-matrix stretching-bending coupling stiffness matrix and D-matrix bending stiffness matrix. Additionally, the normal strains (ε_{ij}°), shear strain (γ_{ij}°) and curvatures (κ_{ij}°) can be written as the functions of the displacement fields and the inner shell radius (R_i) as displayed in eq. (7). Indices x and θ refer to the axial and circumferential directions, respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x^\circ &= \frac{\partial u^\circ}{\partial x} & \varepsilon_\theta^\circ &= \frac{1}{R_i} \left(\frac{\partial v^\circ}{\partial \theta} + w^\circ \right) & \gamma_{x\theta}^\circ &= \frac{1}{R_i} \frac{\partial u^\circ}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v^\circ}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{R_i} \left(v^\circ - \frac{\partial w^\circ}{\partial \theta} \right) \frac{\partial w^\circ}{\partial x} \\ \kappa_x^\circ &= -\frac{\partial^2 w^\circ}{\partial x^2} & \kappa_\theta^\circ &= \frac{-1}{R_i^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w^\circ}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{\partial v^\circ}{\partial \theta} \right) & \kappa_{x\theta}^\circ &= \frac{-1}{R_i} \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 w^\circ}{\partial x \partial \theta} - \frac{\partial v^\circ}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By using the Ritz method to calculate the bending response, the shell displacements ($u^\circ, v^\circ, w^\circ$) in eq. (7) are approximated to be

$$\begin{aligned} u^\circ &= C_{u1} x \cos \theta + C_{u2} x \cos 2\theta + C_{u3} x \cos 3\theta \\ v^\circ &= C_{v1} x^2 \sin \theta + (C_{v2} + C_{v3} x^2) \sin 2\theta \\ w^\circ &= C_{w1} x^2 \cos \theta + (C_{w2} + C_{w3} x^2) \cos 2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Note that the polynomials used for $u^\circ, v^\circ, w^\circ$ are assumed to have a symmetrical deformation with the r - θ plane at the middle point ($x=0$). The both ends are allowed to deform freely. Circular cross-sections along the cylindrical shell can turn into an oval shape on the account of $\sin 2\theta$ and $\cos 2\theta$ in tangential and radial displacements.

2.2 Energy storage in elastic core

The strain energy of the elastic core in eq. (9) is considered as the energy stored in the three dimensional cylindrical solid with the assumptions of zero shear strains in axial direction.

$$U_{core} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{R_i} (\sigma_{r,c} \varepsilon_{r,c} + \sigma_{\theta,c} \varepsilon_{\theta,c} + \tau_{r\theta,c} \gamma_{r\theta,c} + \sigma_{x,c} \varepsilon_{x,c}) r dr d\theta dx \quad (9)$$

The three-dimensional constitutive model of elastic isotropy core is expressed in eq. (10). The strains-displacement relations are shown in eq. (11). Outer surface of elastic core and inner surface of composite shell at $r = R_i$ must deform together through the same distance, thus the displacements of the core inside the hollow cylinder (u_c, v_c, w_c) are the shell displacements scaled proportionally by r/R_i to ensure the identical oval shape at the shell-core interface and no ovalization at the center of core. Note that this radial scaling factor is not applied to the $\sin\theta$ terms in v_c and $\cos\theta$ term in w_c because they solely contribute to the overall flexural deflection of the core, not the cross-sectional dimension change.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{r,c} \\ \sigma_{\theta,c} \\ \sigma_{x,c} \\ \tau_{r\theta,c} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{E_c}{(1+\nu_c)(1-2\nu_c)} \begin{pmatrix} 1-\nu_c & \nu_c & \nu_c & 0 \\ \nu_c & 1-\nu_c & \nu_c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1-\nu_c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & (1-2\nu_c)/2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{r,c} \\ \varepsilon_{\theta,c} \\ \varepsilon_{x,c} \\ \gamma_{r\theta,c} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{x,c} &= \frac{\partial u_c}{\partial x} & \varepsilon_{r,c} &= \frac{\partial w_c}{\partial r} \\ \varepsilon_{\theta,c} &= \frac{w_c}{r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v_c}{\partial \theta} & \gamma_{r\theta,c} &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w_c}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v_c}{\partial r} - \frac{v_c}{r} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_c &= \frac{r}{R_i} (C_{u1}x \cos\theta + C_{u2}x \cos 2\theta + C_{u3}x \cos 3\theta) \\ v_c &= C_{v1}x^2 \sin\theta + \frac{r}{R_i} (C_{v2} + C_{v3}x^2) \sin 2\theta \\ w_c &= C_{w1}x^2 \cos\theta + \frac{r}{R_i} (C_{w2} + C_{w3}x^2) \cos 2\theta \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

From the above energy formulation, coefficients $C_{u1}, C_{u2}, \dots, C_{w3}$ are unknown but are to be determined by minimizing the total potential energy V in eq. (3) for stationary condition. This results in vanishing of the derivative of total potential energy with respect to each unknown coefficient as indicated in eq. (13). Given the value of flexure moment, geometries and material properties of the cylinder and core, we can solve the system of nine nonlinear equilibrium equations for the nine coefficients. Therefore, global bending response can be evaluated numerically.

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial C_{mn}} = 0 \quad ; \quad m = \{u, v, w\} \quad \text{and} \quad n = \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2: Response of cylindrical shell subjected to bending moment

The preliminary computational results are illustrated in Fig. 2 when core-free condition is considered ($E_c = 0$). The material properties used in the calculations are tabulated in Table 1. The global bending response of the quasi-isotropic $[0/90/+45/-45]_s$ laminated shells predicted by the present minimum potential energy model reveals nonlinear moment-curvature characteristics with the maximum critical moment (M_{cr}) very close to that obtained from the second order ovalization model (SOM), which is stated in Introduction. However, the present model can capture a change in the moment-curvature relation due to the effect of cylinder length, whereas SOM cannot because it is created from the assumption of two dimensional ring-type structure. Note that FOM shows noticeably lower critical point, while no ovalization condition ($\zeta = 0$) leads to the linear bending response calculated from classical Euler-Bernoulli beam theory.

Part	E_1 , (GPa)	E_2 , (GPa)	G_{12} , (GPa)	ν_{12}
Shell	24.4	6.87	2.89	0.32
Core	Up to effective properties E_x of the shell			0.28

Table 1: Mechanical properties of materials

3 LOCAL INSTABILITY

Figure 3: Force and Moment resultant of a cylindrical shell element

In addition to the limit point induced by distorted cross-section, local instability can occur on the compression side of the cylinder. Theoretically, the local buckling load on the equilibrium path is examined by solving stability equations or eq. (14) of the cylindrical shell element displayed in Fig.3. The derivation of eq. (14) is carried out by performing stability analysis of pre-buckling state with Trefftz criterion [15]. In the equations subscript “0” is refer to equilibrium state and “1” is refer to pre-buckling state. Term $k_e w_1$ represents the spring-like force exerted on the shell element that are generated from the elastic core. The core is then treated as an elastic foundation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\partial N_{x1}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{x\theta 1}}{R_m \partial \theta} = 0 \\
 & \frac{\partial N_{x\theta 1}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{\theta 1}}{R_m \partial \theta} + \frac{1}{R_m} \left(\frac{\partial M_{\theta 1}}{R_m \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial M_{x\theta 1}}{\partial x} \right) - \frac{1}{R_m} (N_{\theta 0} \beta_{\theta 1} + N_{x\theta 0} \beta_{x1}) = 0 \\
 & \frac{\partial^2 M_{x1}}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{x\theta 1}}{R_m \partial x \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 M_{\theta 1}}{R_m^2 \partial \theta^2} - N_{\theta 1} - N_{x0} \frac{\partial \beta_{x1}}{\partial x} + N_{x\theta 0} \left(\frac{\partial \beta_{\theta 1}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \beta_{x1}}{R_m \partial \theta} \right) + N_{\theta 0} \frac{\partial \beta_{\theta 1}}{R_m \partial \theta} - k_e w_1 = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

3.1 Elastic Foundation Stiffness

To be able to compute the local buckling load, the elastic foundation stiffness (k_e) must be determined. Defined in [14], Maxwell stress function (ϕ) in a three-dimensional elastic isotropic medium is employed. For this problem it is assumed to have magnitude A , wavelength in x -direction $2\pi/\alpha$, wavelength in y -direction $2\pi/\beta$ and decay length parameter in the core thickness direction γ , as expressed in eq. (15).

$$\phi = A \cos(\alpha x) \cos(\beta y) e^{-\gamma z} \quad (15)$$

The stress function must satisfy Laplace's equation in eq. (16). Therefore, the relation between the two wavelength parameters and one decay length parameter can be written in eq. (17).

$$\nabla^2 \phi = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\gamma^2 = \alpha^2 + \beta^2 \quad (17)$$

The stresses and strain may be determined from the stress function as followed in eq. (18) and (19) respectively.

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} \quad \sigma_y = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} \quad \sigma_z = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} \quad (18)$$

$$\varepsilon_z = \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = \frac{\sigma_z - \nu_c (\sigma_x + \sigma_y)}{E_c} \quad (19)$$

The displacement of the shell on elastic foundation w is obtained by integration of strain in the z -direction.

$$w = \int_0^{-\infty} \varepsilon_z dz \quad (20)$$

Lastly, the elastic foundation stiffness in Fig.3 is evaluated from stress to displacement ratio in z -direction as shown in eq. (21).

$$k_e = - \left. \frac{\sigma_z}{w} \right|_{z=0} = - \frac{E_c \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \beta^2}}{(1 - \nu_c)} \quad (21)$$

3.2 Local Buckling Load

As usually done in literature, the local buckling in bent cylindrical shells is assumed to occur when the axial force resultant (N_{x0}) in bending case is equal to the critical axial force resultant of a uniform compressed cylinder with the radius equal to current local hoop radius (R_{eq}) of the equivalent cylinder as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). Therefore, R_m in eq. (14) is replaced with R_{eq} in eq. (22).

$$R_{eq} = \frac{(R_m + w|_{\theta=\pi/2})^2}{R_m + w|_{\theta=0}} \quad (22)$$

To determine the local buckling load the pre-buckling state, force and moment resultants in eq. (14) must be expressed in term of the normal strains (ε_{ij1}), shear strain (γ_{ij1}) and curvatures (κ_{ij1}) by using eq. (6). Note that in contrast to section 2, all of variables in this section are referenced to the middle plane. Thus, for balanced symmetric laminates the values of A_{16} , A_{26} , and all components of B_{ij} in eq. (6) are equal to zero. These strains, curvatures and rotations (β_{ij1}) can be in turn substituted in terms of gradients of displacement functions (u_1, v_1, w_1) as shown in eq. (23).

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{x1} &= \frac{\partial u_1}{x} & \varepsilon_{\theta 1} &= \frac{\partial v_1}{R_{eq} \partial \theta} + \frac{w_1}{R_{eq}} & \gamma_{x\theta 1} &= \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_1}{R_{eq} \partial \theta} \\ \kappa_{x1} &= -\frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial x^2} & \kappa_{\theta 1} &= \frac{\partial v_1}{R_{eq}^2 \partial \theta} - \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{R_{eq}^2 \partial \theta^2} & \kappa_{x\theta 1} &= \frac{1}{R_{eq}} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{R_{eq} \partial x \partial \theta} \\ & & \beta_{\theta 1} &= \frac{v_1}{R_{eq}} - \frac{\partial w_1}{R_{eq} \partial \theta} & \beta_{x1} &= -\frac{\partial w_1}{\partial x} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The displacement functions in pre-buckling state are defined by two waveforms in longitudinal and circumferential directions in eq. (24).

$$u_1 = u_m e^{i\alpha x} e^{i\beta\theta}, \quad v_1 = v_m e^{i\alpha x} e^{i\beta\theta}, \quad w_1 = w_m e^{i\alpha x} e^{i\beta\theta} \quad (24)$$

Effect of the equilibrium state shear force resultant $N_{x\theta 0}$ is always disappeared on compression side because of symmetry at $\theta = 0^\circ$, while the effect of circumferential force resultant ($N_{\theta 0}$) becomes stronger when distorted cross-section is more ovalized. Thus, $N_{\theta 0}$ must be included to calculate the local buckling load. This can be simply done by considering circumferential force resultant as a part of axial force resultant as illustrated in eq. (25).

$$N_{\theta 0} = \frac{\varepsilon_{x0} - a_{11} N_{x0}}{a_{12}}, \quad N_{x\theta 0} = 0 \quad (25)$$

where a_{ij} is inverse of A-matrix. ε_{x0} is longitudinal strain on the middle plane in equilibrium state.

$$\begin{pmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} \\ K_{12} & K_{22} & K_{23} \\ K_{13} & K_{23} & K_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_m \\ v_m \\ w_m \end{Bmatrix} e^{i\alpha x} e^{i\beta\theta} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

After Substituting eqs. (21)-(25) into eq. (14) and rearranging terms, a linear system of equations expressed in eq. (26) can be obtained. The nontrivial solution of K-Matrix in eq. (26) shows that the axial force resultant (N_{x0}) for local instability is functions of stretching stiffness coefficient (A_{ij}), bending stiffness coefficient (D_{ij}), equivalent radius (R_{eq}), axial strain at the middle plane (ε_{x0}) and wavelengths (α, β).

The critical value of axial force resultant is happen at critical wavelengths (α_{cr}, β_{cr}) when the derivative of axial force resultant with respect to their wavelengths are equal to zero. The local buckling occurs if and only if the axial force resultant reached the critical value ($N_{x0,cr}$).

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The calculated bending responses of quasi-isotropic laminate composite cylindrical shells with and without an elastic core are shown in Fig.4. The core examined in this case is very soft because its

Young's modulus is one millionth of the effective modulus of the cylinder. When the applied moment is low, the deformations are small and the circular cross-sections are almost intact. The initial slopes for both cases, therefore, are linear and equal to each other, since the presence of the elastic core does not play a role in resisting the cross-sectional shape change. After the load is increased, deformations become larger, the cylindrical shell with an elastic core shows higher resistance to ovalization and maintain longer linear range, whereas the one with no core ovalizes more and rapidly lose bending stiffness until the moment reaches maximum point at C. As can be seen, the critical moment of the cylinder reinforced with core at D is almost two times as high as the critical moment at C, even the weak core stiffness aforementioned.

Figure 4: Bending responses of cylindrical shell with and without elastic core

Figure 5: (a) Bending responses; (b) critical and local buckling moment of angle-ply laminates and quasi-isotropic laminate cylindrical shell

The local buckling moments are also determined and illustrated in the figure as point F and E for the cylinder with core and without core, respectively. The local buckling moment if the core is present is still higher than that with absence of core, but it is not as high compared to the critical moments. This is because geometry of the curved shell is more influential to local deformations than the support from weak elastic foundation. In addition, local instability occurs before the critical moment so the cylinders are more vulnerable to local buckling in these two cases. The simulations from the finite-element software ABAQUSTM agree very well with the bending responses obtained from the present minimum potential energy principle and exhibit structural collapse right at the local buckling load calculated from the model developed herein.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 6: Critical moment, local buckling moment and relative moment of quasi-isotropic and 45 degree angle ply laminate

Effect of fiber orientation to bending response are illustrated in Fig. 5. The initial slope of 0° degree of angle-ply laminate is higher than 90° of angle-ply laminate, since the bending stiffness is high when fibers are placed parallel to the longitudinal axis of the cylinder and it is low when fibers are aligned in the hoop direction as shown in Fig.5a. The critical moment and local buckling moment are decreased when the fiber direction deviates from the longitudinal axis as shown in Fig.5b in range of 0° to 45°, because the flexural stiffness is lower. However, in range of 45° to 90° of angle-ply the more oriented fibers in the circumferential direction the more resistance to the distortion of the cross-section. Consequently, the critical moment and local buckling moment are increased as seen in Fig.5b. This phenomenon indicates that the stiffnesses in both longitudinal and circumferential directions are important and it provides the reason why quasi-isotropic laminate only slightly suffers from the fiber orientations in some layers that are directed away from 0° and 90°.

Fig. 6 shows geometrical and relative core modulus effects on the critical limit point and local instability point. In cases of constant mean radius, critical moment and local buckling moment become higher when shell thickness is thicker. The same conclusion can be seen when the modulus of elastic core is higher. Upon closer inspection, Fig.6(a) and 6(b) indicates that Young's modulus of the core has more influence on the critical load of thinner shells than the thicker shells. This is due to the effective longitudinal modulus of the shell is normally much higher than the elastic modulus of the core. The angle-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates give the similar characteristics.

According Fig.6(c) and 6(d), thin shells have far lower local buckling moment than thick shells because force resultant in thin shell is higher than thick shell at the same value of moment. Young's modulus of elastic core has insignificant effect on the local buckling of the very thin shells, thus the analysis of local instability can be simplified by neglecting the presence of the core in the very thin cylinders. The structure with more flexible shell in Fig.6 (d) is even less sensitive to modulus of the core.

Effective of filling of elastic core are shown by relative value of ratio of local buckling moment to critical moment in Fig.6(e) and 6(f). When the value is less than 1 the cylinder will have failure from local buckling. In case of optimization, these two failures of the structure should be forced to occur at the same value or as close as possible. So, the thin shell shouldn't filled with higher core modulus.

5 CONCLUSION

The bending responses of composite cylindrical structure filled with an elastic core subjected to pure bending has been presented. Responses of balanced and symmetrically laminated composite cylindrical shell with an elastic core are solved by using the minimum potential energy principle and the Ritz's method. Ultimate theoretical capacity of the cylinder depends on two instability modes (ovalization and local buckling). The ovalization equilibrium path of the cylinder is examined directly from the energy equation but local buckling was examined concomitantly by tracking values of force resultants along the equilibrium path and compared them with the critical axial and circumferential force resultant in equivalent cylinder having the congruent radius of the oval. The elastic core was considered as a spring with an elastic spring coefficient k_e in the equivalent cylinder. It is concluded that geometries and properties affect bending response. There are several ways to enhance ovalization critical moment and local buckling moment such as increasing shell thickness, upgrading core stiffness, or aligning the fiber orientation in longitudinal and hoop directions. Increment of critical moment and local buckling are not equally in the same degree. Normally the ovalization critical moment is more responsive than that of the local instability.

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